

Acousmatic, Invisible, Ontology 2

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Abstract

This paper aims at studying the relationship between the invisibility of acousmatic music and the heideggerian theory of being-in-the-world. In the EMS21, we were talking about “Understanding” and “State-of-mind”. We now examine the two last items of the structural whole of care: falling and discourse.

Falling means that we onto-logically have choice: this generally implies that things which are not chosen become invisible. Among all the possible choices, one is particularly important: the choice between “being-in-fault” and “ownmost potentiality-for-being”. Acousmatic music exposes this choice by its very being. But “being-in-fault” and “ownmost potentiality-for-being” depend on discourse.

Does acousmatic music onto-logically belong to discourse, and how, as art, does it show the invisible in discourse? To answer these questions, we must compare art and language, firstly between them, secondly regarding to the expression of invisible and regarding to the specificity of acousmatic music among all arts. Then we will examine if acousmatic music belongs to discourse following its characteristics according to Heidegger: what the discourse is about (what is talked about); what is said-in-the-talk, as such; the communication; and the making-known.

1. Introduction

In the EMS21, we studied the relationship between acousmatic music and the Heideggerian theory of Being. After the state-of-mind and understanding items, now this paper aims at studying this relation with the two other items of what he called structural whole of care: falling (or being in fault) and discourse, and how they express the invisible.

Before going on, we must recall two important points to keep in mind:

- “... not only the matter, the sound, is invisible, but also [...] the invisible becomes the main topic of acousmatic music¹.”
- “acousmatic music has the power to express all these invisibilities in their characteristic of invisibility².”

¹DI SANTO Jean-Louis, “Acousmatic, invisible, ontology”, EMS21

²Ibid.

In a first time, we are going to study falling in relation with its opposite, the ownmost potentiality-for-being. They both drive us to this question: does acousmatic music ontologically belong to discourse? The answer implies what Heidegger called “Poetry”, and certain kinds of invisible.

2. Falling and ownmost potentiality-for-Being

According to Heidegger, falling is onto-logically constitutive of Dasein (being confronted with existence), and is its first way of being. It hides its opposite, the ownmost potentiality-for-Being. This one can only happen by the “call” which can be heard by “hearing”.

2.1 falling

According to Heidegger, being-in-fault is an onto-logic part of Dasein. Being-in-fault doesn't mean making a mistake: it means that choosing onto-logically belongs to Being-in-the-world: by making a choice, we necessarily abandon all the other possibilities. In other terms, what you leave will always remain invisible. And the invisibility of acousmatic music shows by definition what will never appear and thus shows the presence of this invisibility. For example, if you hear a train in an acousmatic piece, you know it is a train. But it is impossible to know exactly which train it is: you can only imagine your train, making a choice among all the possible trains. Besides, the recorded sound is not the original sound: being recorded by a human intention, it becomes a sign. “Ceci n'est pas une pipe” wrote Magritte under a pipe painting: it is just a representation of a pipe. And the re-present-ation of the object mainly shows the absence of this object. Acousmatic music, being invisible, also represents this absence in itself.

Among all choices which Dasein can do, there is one more particularly important: falling in the “idle talk” or searching its ownmost potentiality-for-Being. This specific aspect of falling, the “they” and the “idle talk”, implies adherence to received ideas: the interpretation of the world, as understanding, is already there. The they hides the Being-one's-self. It is the natural way of Dasein's being:

“In no case is a Dasein, untouched and unsexed by this way in which things have been interpreted, set before the open country of a world-in-itself, so that it just beholds what it encounters³.”

Dasein is always thrown in a certain conception of the world that exists before him, and is also thrown in a language and words that are thinking the world in a particular manner. In this way, not only the real world always stays invisible, but also Dasein to himself. Until the invention of “musique concrète”, music was made of notes, rhythms, and with instruments. So music was implicitly meaning “making notes with voice and instruments”. A music made with recorded sounds has broken this traditional conception of music and dropped out the idle talk. In this way, acousmatic music re-opened the conception of music, and also re-opened the perception of the world by using recorded sounds in the world, that is to say symbols. As we are going to see further, these symbols allow to see the world with new eyes, if we can say.

³HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and Time*, p. 213

But Dasein can fall out falling and find its ownmost potentiality-for-being thanks to the “call”:

When the call is understood with an existentiell kind of hearing, such understanding is more authentic the more non-relationally Dasein hears and understands its own Being-appealed-to, and the less the meaning of the call gets perverted by what one says or by what is fitting and accepted [was sich gehOrt und gilt]⁴.

2.2 – ownmost potentiality-for-Being

The call is calling Dasein to its ownmost potentiality-for-Being. Acousmatic music was different from cultural musical practices as we have seen above and, for this reason, it was out of the idle talk, it contained in itself its “ownmost potentiality-for-being”. A music purely based on all sound types, and not only instrumental sounds, renewed the vocabulary and musical grammar, as well as the symbolic significance of the music. It has to find its own way and to explore its own possibilities from a formal and a semantic point of view.

But not only: in acousmatic music, the different levels of structure are strictly related to the perceptive properties of the sounds. Of course, concerning instrumental music, we can say, for example, that Webern built structures that emanated from basic motives. But acousmatic music uses any property of sound, and the overall form results from these properties. By building a form only based on the sound properties it uses, an acousmatic piece is reaching its “ownmost potentiality-for-being”: its development depends on its own material. In this way, it is the mirror of a Dasein seeking himself.

The choice between falling and ownmost potentiality-for-Being depends on hearing: “To the call of conscience there corresponds a possible hearing⁵.”

2.3 – Hearing

We must now examine what hearing consists of. According to Heidegger:

“Hearing is constitutive for discourse. And just as linguistic utterance is based on discourse, so is acoustic perception on hearing. Listening to... is Dasein's existential way of Being-open as Being-with for Others. Indeed, hearing constitutes the primary and authentic way in which Dasein is open for its ownmost potentiality-for-Being...”⁶

Here we can notice that hearing opens on self-understanding as well as on the understanding of others and the world. Symmetrically, a non-hearing opens on a non-understanding: “Both talking and hearing are based upon understanding⁷.” Hearing is turned both inward and outward. Inside Dasein, these two aspects are intertwined insofar as they are located in consciousness. The opening depends on hearing that is part of discourse. What about the music?

Of course, every kind of music and the language itself are based on hearing. But acousmatic music is also based on reduced listening and was born from “*démarche concrète*” which consists

⁴Ibid. p. 325

⁵Ibid. p. 314

⁶Ibid. p. 206

⁷Ibid. p. 208

of a round-trip between listening and composition. Are these two kinds of hearing a particular reflect of the existentiell hearing?

We already discussed of “reduced listening” in the EMS21: we demonstrated that it fully belongs to “understanding”, and thus to discourse. To say it quickly, reduced listening has its own sight⁸. Concerning the “démarche concrète”, we can notice that the composer is there hearing himself composing. If this kind of hearing opens on the ownmost potentiality-for-being, as seen above, it also opens on an understanding the musical piece which is still in work. In this case, the composer is hearing both the sounds he uses and the result of this use, and his “sonic attunement”⁹ or his own experience as composer. According to Hegel, the artwork have two ways of being: on one side, it is the expression of the composer’s interiority, and on the other side, it is a totally autonomous object. This comprehension of both the self-expression and the functioning of the musical piece as an external object fully corresponds to the definition of hearing and illustrates this Heidegger’s sentence:

“We can make clear the connection of discourse with understanding and intelligibility by considering an existential possibility which belongs to talking itself-hearing¹⁰.”

Hearing is fundamentally constitutive of acousmatic music. We can also add this remark: the disappearance of the visible in acousmatic music stresses the importance of hearing.

3. Acousmatic music as artwork dealing with invisibility (Poetry)

In a first step, we must know if there is something in common between acousmatic music and language, that is to say what their nature is. Music belongs to what Heidegger called “Poetry”.

“Poetry is here thought in such a broad sense, and at the same time in such an intimate and essential unity with language and the word, that it must remain open whether art, in all its modes from architecture to poesy, exhausts the nature of poetry¹¹.”

This “intimate and essential unity with language”, if it is already part of the answer, leads us to question the relationship between art and language. We thus first must know what is common between poetry and language as discourse. Then, it will be possible to analyse the specificity of acousmatic music regarding to its invisibility. But what does Heidegger call poetry?

⁸“The reduced listening aims at revealing sound features in order to create a coherent musical architecture.”

⁹MAESTRI Eric, “Composition as an Act and Existential Trace”

¹⁰HEIDEGGER Martin, op. Cit. p. 206

¹¹HEIDEGGER Martin, “The origin of the work of art”, *Off the beaten track*, p. 46

3.1. Art and poetry

“... *Art is, then, a becoming and happening of truth* [...] *All art*, as the letting happen of the advent of the truth of beings, is, in essence, poetry¹².”

What Heidegger is calling “truth” is a suitability not between the real and its enunciation, but between Dasein and its expression. In this sense, it reveals the truth of Being ordinary concealed. Acousmatic music, which is a kind of poetry, expresses this truth as invisibility.

“In virtue of the projection of the unconcealedness of beings which is set into the work and casts itself toward us, everything ordinary and hitherto existing becomes an unbeing¹³.”

In recorded sounds, “every thing ordinary” becomes “an unbeing” in two ways. The first way is the common way of art where the object is projected out of the ordinary: the ordinary conceals its truth. Thanks to art, “an open place is thrown open, a place in which everything is other than it was¹⁴.” The example given by Heidegger is the Van Gogh’s painting of peasant shoes. This ordinary object is an everyday piece of equipment. But, by the power of art,

“This equipment belongs *to the Earth* and finds protection in the *world* of the peasant woman. From out of this protected belonging the equipment itself rises to its resting-within-itself¹⁵.”

Its use and usefulness disappear, and the pair of shoes becomes an unbeing. In this way, the Being of this pair of shoes is disclosed.

The second way, where the object is projected out of the ordinary by being totally invisible, only belongs to acousmatic music. The disappearance of the object drop it out of the ordinary, and it becomes an unbeing by concealment. By this invisibility we realise that we usually don’t see it like it is and that, in order to be perceive, it appears by concealment to show what we don’t see. We just hear it. And we have seen that hearing opens on understanding and on ownmost potentiality-for-being.

Art, as poetry, reveals the concealed truth of objects. What is the “intimate and essential unity” between art and language? What is the status of invisible in art?

3.2. Poetry and language

Considering art and language from an onto-logical point of view, Heidegger has defined each of them. Firstly:

“What poetry, as clearing projection, unfolds of unconcealment and projects into the rift within the figure is the open; ... in the midst of beings, it brings them to shine and sound¹⁶.”

¹²Ibid. p. 44

¹³Ibid. p. 44/45

¹⁴Ibid. p. 44

¹⁵Ibid. p. 14

¹⁶Ibid. p. 45

Here we can notice the importance, concerning our purpose, of sound, while, secondly:

“Language itself is poetry in the essential sense. But [since] language is that happening in which, each time, beings are first disclosed as beings¹⁷...”

Even if we can notice a difference between art and language, where the language “is poetry in the essential sense”, we can clearly see that the common function of art and language is to disclose beings. Disclosing supposes that something was hidden. Concerning music, this disclosing implies hearing. And hearing something concealed implies an acousmatic situation. What is concealed?

3.3. Art and invisibility

If language is mainly turned toward “beings... as beings”, art as poetry is turned toward “the figure of the open”. Heidegger describes this openness as follows:

“The world is the self-opening openness of the broad paths of simple and essential decisions in the destiny of a historical people. The earth is the unforced coming forth of the continually self-closing, and in that way, self-sheltering. World and earth are essentially different and yet never separated from one another. World is grounded on earth, and earth rises up through world¹⁸.”

According to Heidegger: “The work-being of the work consists in fighting the fight between world and earth¹⁹.” What he called

“Earth is that which cannot be forced, that which is effortless and untiring. On and in the earth, historical man finds his dwelling in the world²⁰.”

and

“World is that always-nonobjectual to which we are subject²¹.”

The Earth constantly withdraws into itself, refusing to reveal itself. The World, because it is openness, admits no secrets: a battle ensues from this conflict. This struggle, with no winner or loser, brings concealment to light. The reason of the fight is that “Earth shatters every attempt to penetrate it²².” In other words, what is invisible must stay invisible, and we saw that the main topic of acousmatic music is the invisible. But even more so: in acousmatic music, Earth is present in two ways. On one hand, it manifests itself through the phenomenon of sound, as in any music or language. On the other hand, through the possibility of recording, it is expressed by natural sounds or those of matter. But this presence doesn’t mean unveiling:

“Each being which we encounter and which encounters us maintains this strange opposition of presence in that at the same time it always holds itself back in a

¹⁷Ibid. p. 46

¹⁸Ibid. p.26

¹⁹Ibid. p. 27

²⁰Ibid. p. 24

²¹Ibid. p. 23

²²Ibid. p. 25

concealment. Concealment, however, reigns in the midst of beings, in a twofold manner²³.”

The fight opposes pure existence against the desire for knowledge. Something appears to show what doesn't appear. Heidegger specifies what these two ways are:

- The refusal: it is what only appears, revealing its existence without revealing what it is:

“Concealment as refusal is not primarily or only the limit of knowledge in each particular case; it is, rather, the beginning of the clearing of what is illuminated²⁴.”

It is particularly the case in an acousmatic situation, when something reveals its presence only by sounding. A sound is already something which is appearing by disappearing. And a recorded sound also hides its cause. In this sense, it is refusal.

- The “obstructing”:

“But concealment, though of course of another sort, also occurs within the illuminated. Beings push themselves in front of others, the one hides the other, this casts that into shadow, a few obstruct many, on occasion one denies all. Concealment, here, is not simple refusal. Rather, a being indeed appears but presents itself as other than it is. This concealment is an obstructing²⁵.”

What is, is revealed under another identity, for example a symbol, necessarily the case in acousmatic music. Here, the obstructing works in two ways. Firstly, of course, the recorded sound hides its cause. The real object disappears and its representation depends on the listener imagination and history. The representation that appears is put “instead-of” the real object. And secondly, if we consider the sound in a symbolic way, either the actual sound disappear, or the object for which it is intended does not appear.

The recorded sound, through the phenomenon of disengagement (Greimas 1993), refers back invisibly to both the cause and context of the sound, and the original sound. The real cause, whether it exists in the environment or in the recording studio, is replaced by another cause, which is the composer's will and desire inside the piece's context. In the case of a studio recording for a composition, one could argue that there is unity between the cause of the recording and the recorded sound, which is the composer's intention. But even in this case, who can know the composer's real motivations? He records the result of his expression and not its causes (his unconscious, in the broadest sense, for example). This is already a re-presentation. These primary causes, extracted from their context, will disappear in the context of the composition and are relegated to the past.

On the other hand, the recorded sound is not the original sound. If we consider sound as a “phonography”, i.e. a photograph of the original sound, we can see differences similar to those in an image where the actual size of the object is often lost. A recording differs, even if only very slightly, from the original sound. The recording/broadcasting system is never completely neutral and “colours” the sound. The recorded sound therefore plunges the original sound and its cause into invisibility, either by refusal or by obstructing. Its broadcast reveals the existence of what was at the same time as it hides it.

²³Ibid. p. 30

²⁴Ibid. p. 30

²⁵Ibid. p. 30

Moreover, recorded sound, as concealment, exists in three temporal dimensions: as a representation of the original sound, for itself in its present, and as an “instead-of” concerning its purpose. It exists as a concatenation of the past, present, and future. We have just seen that the cause and context, and the original sound belong to the past.

In its present reality, the broadcast sound directly encounters the mystery of the Earth through the sensation of its pure presence, which reinforces the sensation of presence of the listener who perceives it according to his history (the phthongos²⁶: the sound-living-body that will signify). According to Hegel,

“We need a material which for our apprehension is without stability and even as it arises and exists vanishes once more²⁷.”

Sound appears by disappearing, and this mode of being emphasises “refusal”; its signifying function shows that it hides by appearing instead-of what is relegated to the invisible. Through instead-of, it is a form of obstructing.

The sound that is presently present²⁸ imposes itself through its own presence, but also refers to the presence in the absence of its source and its instead-of. What Hegel has told about language can be applied to music:

“Sound articulating itself further for determinate representations, speech, and its system, language, give to sensations, intuitions, representations a second, higher reality than their immediate one, in general an existence that carries weight in the realm of representation²⁹.”

In its future reality, the meaning of sound functions through an ad libitum instead-of and through pro-jection, that is, a new meaning linked to its shape and matter, and through denotation or connotation. The meaning depends on the listener's past, the composer being here his own listener. The musical meaning, the instead-of, may remain obscure or be partially explained. This meaning can exist strictly in the present or can be deployed in the future; but these present and future have their roots in the listener's past. Besides, this future interpretation implies three kinds of past: the one of the piece hearing, the one of the sound's recording and the one of the listener.

The recorded sound functions by refusal or obstructing in its three temporal dimensions: it plunges the past into the unknown, reveals its mystery in its presence and its meaning takes place in a future through the past. Obstructing therefore belongs primarily to the past and the future, since either its origin or its purpose is hidden by the recorded sound, while refusal is established primarily in the present, since the Earth here expresses itself directly through its matter, and it disappears when it appears. But the sound that is presently present also functions

²⁶What we call phthongos is the vibration of matter captured by the matter of our bodies, transformed into nerve impulses within the auditory system and then interpreted by the brain. That is to say, both sound as a possibility of matter, that of the Earth and that of our bodies, and as the perception of the perceiving subject linked to its history (his personal history and the history of the people to whom he belongs).

²⁷HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Aesthetics lecture on fine arts*, translated by T. M. Knox, Oxford university press, London, 1975, p. 889

²⁸Heidegger was thinking that there are two kinds of present: the presently present and the present in absence.

²⁹HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Hegel's philosophy of mind*, translated by W. Wallace and A. V. Miller, revised by M. J. Inwood, Clarendon press, Oxford, 2007, p.195

by obstructing, since it is put instead of its object. In acousmatic music, this temporal labyrinth is part of concealment and unconcealment (see figure below).

Figure 1: “Temporal labyrinth”. We can notice that, concerning the listener, the historical, social and personal composer history, as well as the cause and context of recordings, are replaced by historical, social and personal listener history. Besides, the listener’s interpretation also depends on the interpretant he uses: emotional, energetic or logic (Peirce). We can also notice the constant presence of Earth.

Another kind of invisibility is the habit: it hides the truth of objects, and arts reveals it by the “beginning”:

“Bestowal and grounding have in themselves the abruptness of what we call a beginning.... A beginning, by contrast, always contains the undisclosed fullness of the extraordinary, and that means the strife with the ordinary³⁰.”

³⁰HEIDEGGER Martin, *Off the beaten track*, p. 48

If we come to Heidegger example, the Van Gogh painting, we get a full explanation of the beginning's mechanism. The first step consists in hiding the truth of the object by its use:

“The individual piece of equipment becomes worn out and used up. But also, customary usage itself falls into disuse, becomes ground down and merely habitual. In this way equipmental being withers away, sinks to the level of mere equipment³¹.”

In a second step, the object is removed from everyday life through the artwork. Here, it is no more possible to see it as a usual object. Firstly because a painting is not an object you can easily put on your feet to protect them! Secondly, because being “useless”, the reason for the artwork existence does not lie in its usefulness, but in what it reveals. So it slides from the invisibility of its ordinary to the extraordinary.

“In the work of art, the truth of the being has set itself to work. "Set" means here: to bring to stand. In the work, a being, a pair of peasant shoes, comes to stand in the light of its being. The being of the being comes into the constancy of its shining³².”

In acousmatic music, the ordinary also regains its originality through its erasure. It becomes surprising by its disappearance. Taken out of sight, its ephemeral trace, sound, causes it to appear in the mind as an extra-ordinary object, by hearing. Being invisible, it reveals, in a sense, its “ownmost potentiality-for-being”. Isn't this, in its own way, the meaning of the word acousmatic? Music, it shows what it eludes. Within poetry, it brings the invisible, concealment or beginning, to discovery in its purest power of being.

We now can say that art has a very specific relation with the invisible. And, among art, acousmatic music takes a very specific place according to its very invisibility.

Art and language disclose being, but art is turned toward concealment and invisibility. So, art and language are different but have a common part on an other side. Is it sufficient to consider acousmatic music as discourse?

4. Acousmatic music as discourse

We now must examine the heideggerian definition of discourse, and see if and how acousmatic music can belong to it. He wrote:

“The items constitutive for discourse are: what the discourse is about (what is talked about); what is said-in-the-talk, as such; the communication; and the making-known³³.”

Let us analyse each item:

4.1. what the discourse is about

This item concerns the subject of the enunciation, and corresponds to the referential function of the language. Here we can find a difference between music and language: we can say that language expresses what the discourse is about by words or, using Ch. Sanders Peirce semiotics,

³¹Ibid. p. 15

³²Ibid. p.16

³³HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and Time*, p. 206

by symbols, while music is meaning by icons. For this reason, François Bayle was speaking of “i-sounds” (i-sons). But if this term stresses the semiotic aspect of the sounds, I prefer to underline its significant function, into a piece, by the word ideophthegm³⁴:

“the ideophthegm presents itself as all recorded sound taken as material and bearing meaning in order to express an intention of the mind (idea, feeling, symbol...)”³⁵.

Music can express by the sound shape and matter, by denotation or by connotation of recorded sounds.

This conception of sound-meaning is not new, and we can hypothesise that it was probably already existing in prehistory: art in general and music in particular are said to have originated in the sacred realm. More recently, many authors has already noticed it. The M.I.M. laboratory elaborated the concept of Temporal Semiotics Units, Denis Smalley, by his spectromorphology, defined some semantic figures, and so on... Our purpose, by the term of ideophthegm, is to include sounds in a meaningful chain, like words, in order to make the “musical discourse” manifest.

Concerning acousmatic music, sounds, usually clues to their source, i.e. ready-to-hand as reference, become signs when they are recorded.

“Signs also arise when one takes as a sign [Zum-Zeichen-nehmen] something that is ready-to-hand already”³⁶.

That is particularly the case in acousmatic music, and we can notice that Pierre Schaeffer himself was talking about the significance of sounds:

“If I gather together the bursts of noise, the cries of animals, the modulated sound of machines, I also strive to articulate them like the words of a language, which I would practice without even understanding it, and without ever having learned it; I decipher hieroglyphs”³⁷.

Of course, the musical discourse, and even the music acousmatic discourse, doesn’t have the precision of the linguistic discourse. But it is very interesting to note that Schaeffer already understood the semantic potential of acousmatic music, even if its meaning does not clearly appear and needs to be interpreted.

³⁴This word is built with the ancient Greek words *eidos* (shape, idea) and *phthegma* (sound). A sonic ideogram, if we can say.

³⁵DI SANTO Jean-Louis, *Invisible musique: le chant de l’existence*, p. 65

“Ainsi l’idéophthegme se présente comme tout son enregistré pris comme matériau et porteur de signification en vue d’exprimer une intention de l’esprit (idée, sentiment, symbole...)”

³⁶HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and time*, p. 111

³⁷SCHAEFFER Pierre, *A la recherche d’une musique concrète*, p. 101.

“Si je rassemble les éclats du bruit, les cris des animaux, le son modulé des machines, je m’efforce moi aussi, de les articuler comme les mots d’un langage, que je pratiquerais sans même le comprendre, et sans jamais l’avoir appris ; je déchiffre des hiéroglyphes.”

4.2. what is said-in-the-talk, as such

Globally, what is said-in-the-talk is made of vocabulary, ie sounds, and grammar, ie structures, even if Heidegger does not mention it. In other words, it concerns everything in the talk, except the meaning:

“We do not so much understand the entities which are talked about; we already are listening only to what is said-in-the-talk as such³⁸.”

The features of pure sounds of language are clearly described by the philosopher:

“Being-in and its state-of-mind are made known in discourse and indicated in language by intonation, modulation, the tempo of talk, “the way of speaking”³⁹.”

Modulation, intonation, tempo... are an important part of music. This is well known, and we will not dwell on this aspect. But sound is possible because it is already contained in the matter, and in the matter that composes our body, by its vibratory properties. Acousmatic music recalls this possibility of the earth. In acousmatic music, what is said-in-the-talk both belongs to the Earth and to the World. The part of Earth can be underlined by recording natural elements, of course, but also by sounds machines where we can also hear the matter itself. Recorded sounds can also express what is said-in-the-talk in non human sounds.

“After using different forms of writing, revealing the notion of sound “nature” through sounds from all sources... there remained the rich world of noises caused by human activities, which I will call “artificial” to distinguish them from “natural” noises. ... By listening to sound material, through our interpretations and expressions, we transform the inside into the outside⁴⁰.”

This fusion between inside and outside illustrates what Heidegger called “involvement”. By this mechanism, non-human sounds can express human feelings or human thought.

Even if Heidegger doesn't mention grammar, it is constitutive of language and its oral expression. Concerning language, grammar is not directly manifest by hearing. But concerning music, we can directly *hear* grammar: theme and variation, modulation, and so on. This grammar can be the support of meaning, and the expression of state-of-mind as well as sound. Moreover, speaking more specifically about acousmatic music, François Bayle was writing:

“All the abilities of a technique that substitutes the object for its image, acquire the status of a rhetoric. Montage, extraction, insertion, illustration, magnification, but also breaking of time, bursting of places, but still mixing, overprinting, metamorphosis of contours, but finally introduction of speed and space, then become together means and contents, medium and message⁴¹.”

What is said-in-the-talk, as such, that is to say sounds and grammar in music, mainly expresses state-of-mind, but also concerns the being-with.

³⁸HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and time*, p. 212

³⁹Ibid. p. 205

⁴⁰PARMEGIANI Bernard, *Dedans-Dehors*, 1977, creation presented on february 28 1977 at Palais des Arts, Paris

⁴¹BAYLE François, « La musique acousmatique ou l'art des sons projetés », *Musique acousmatique, propositions... positions*, p. 51

4.3. the communication

According to Heidegger, the communication is possible because the possibility of communication already exists inside Dasein, and because Dasein is already Being-in-the-world:

“Likewise, when we are explicitly hearing the discourse of another, we proximally understand what is said, or – to put it more exactly – we are already with him, in advance, alongside the entity which the discourse is about⁴².”

In this way, any information can be shared. This is an important aspect common to music and language. What is the content of this communication?

“In this more general kind of communication, the Articulation of Being with one another understandingly is constituted. Through it a co-state-of-mind [Mitbefindlichkeit] gets “shared”, and so does the understanding of Being-with⁴³.”

So communication exists in two levels: the first level concerns the state-of-mind and the second level concerns understanding. If we separate these two concepts for the purposes of analysis, let us not forget that, according to Heidegger, they are inseparable: “Understanding always has its mood⁴⁴.” We have quickly seen above how state-of-mind was shared in acousmatic music, and how ideophthegms were linked with understanding. Alessandro Bertinetto described this phenomenon more precisely:

"In art and music, the modes of expression of the material and the formal and structural configurations of signs are “charged” with meaning. It is not a question of communicating pre-formed content through a “transparent” medium, but rather of exploiting the formal and material communication possibilities of these means and inventing modes of communication for content that could not otherwise be expressed... Any formal element can correspond to cognitive correlates by virtue of symbolic associations and analogies awakened by its expressive, affective, and even formal qualities⁴⁵.”

On the one hand, musical communication does not rely on socially established codes, such as language, and therefore loses some of its precision. But on the other hand, Bertinetto tells us that what is expressed through art cannot be expressed in any other way. Art in general, and music in particular, expresses the unspeakable. In other words, music communicates what cannot be communicated in any other way. Acousmatic music, which can use all the sounds of the world, offers the maximum possibility of relation between inside and outside. In this way, it has the power to summon the Earth, and for this reason offers a wide range of symbolic possibilities. This openness promotes the communication of being-with as being-in-the-world.

⁴²HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and time*, p. 207

⁴³Ibid. p. 205

⁴⁴Ibid. p. 182

⁴⁵BERTINETTO, Alessandro, *Pensée des sons. Thèmes de philosophie de la musique*, p. 101

4.4. the making-known

According to Eric Maestri,

“The discourse that takes place through music, composed of sounds, comes into contact with the whole of the gamut of possibilities endowed with meaning. This discourse is inhabited by all the other discourse that inhabit the possible experience of the listeners. Music becomes part of their experience, nourishing the hermeneutic circle of each one⁴⁶.”

In this way, the making known of acousmatic music, by hiding the visible, shows the invisibility of all these other discourses. These common references promote being-with, in a subterranean way, if we can say so. These shared, but “under-toned”, discourses and experiences are the condition of communication – the action of making something common. But as Bertinetto told us, it does not immediately reveal itself in music. However its difficulty in grasping does not mean its absence: just its invisibility.

The simple reference is not enough for the sign: it must take place in a whole signifying network in order to fully realise its referential function. But the message also implies the articulation of meaning.

For this reason,

“Discourse is the Articulation of intelligibility... That which can be Articulated in interpretation, and thus even more primordially in discourse, is what we have called "meaning". That which gets articulated as such in discursive Articulation, we call the "totality-of-significations" [Bedeutungsganze]⁴⁷.”

In language, the meaning is given by words articulated between them, which are relatively precise. But even in this case, they are interpreted. According to Nelson Goodman (1968), an artwork is recognisable by its syntactic and semantic density. In acousmatic music, the meaning is given by articulated ideophthegms. Here, the message manifests itself through concealment, an entanglement within other words. Through a set of ad libitum references, the meaning is both diluted and reverberated in multiple echoes. Always, one meaning can hide another, riving each listener to the "scandal of his contingency⁴⁸". In return, as seen above, music can tell the unspeakable.

Moreover, the communication of feelings, that is to say the making-known of feelings and by feelings, takes a very important place in music, and is part of the unspeakable. For example, if you easily understand the meaning of the word “joy”, that has nothing to do with feeling “joy”. And if a composer wants to explain “joy” to his listeners, he must pay attention both to sounds he uses and to the structure of the piece:

“The composer for his part can of course put into his work a specific meaning, a content consisting of ideas and feelings and their articulated and complete succession... Music is therefore more profound when the composer gives the

⁴⁶MAESTRI Eric, “Composition as an Act and Existential Trace”, *Perspectives of new music volume 59*, 2021

⁴⁷HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and Time*, p. 203/204

⁴⁸GAGNEBIN Murielle, *Pour une esthétique psychanalytique. L'artiste stratège de l'inconscient*, PUF, Paris, 1994, p. 196

same attention even in instrumental music to both sides, to the expression of a content (true, a rather vague one) and to the musical structure...⁴⁹”

In music, the making-know concerns ideas as well as feelings, or understanding and state-of-mind, and, according to Hegel, the articulation of these two sides with structures.

So, we can find in acousmatic music the four items constitutive for discourses. We clearly see, now, that it onto-logically belongs to discourse with its own specificity: disclosing the invisible in different manners, but still being invisible.

5. Conclusion

Being still largely unknown, acousmatic music is out of the “idle talk” conception of music. In this sense, it is very appropriate to reveal “falling”. Besides, it “put in work” the ownmost-potentiality-for-Being” by the piece structure itself. Its invisibility disclose the invisible contained in poetry and stresses the power of “hearing”. As discourse, by means of understanding and co-state-of-mind, it reveals Being-in-the-world.

Of course, each every day life act is “existential” by essence. But only acousmatic music can disclose the existence of invisible inside Being, as invisible, by hearing. Acousmatic music also expresses the unspeakable invisible, the feelings, the feeling of being-there, and feeling the presence of our existence’s mysteries.

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⁴⁹HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Aesthetics, lecture on fine arts*, Vol II, translated by T. M. Knox, Oxford at the Clarendon press, 1975, p. 954

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